

Observe and Revisit: Procedural Music Generation with Cellular Automata on Quantum Hardware

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Abstract. This paper presents a procedural music generation quantum computing system and respective bespoke compositional methods developed to compose “Observe” and “Revisit”, two movements of “Qubism”, a piece for chamber orchestra and electronics. The system implements a dynamical system model known as a Partitioned Quantum Cellular Automaton, or PQCA. The compositional method translates the time-based behaviour of the PQCA into musical patterns. The music was generated with a PQCA built with 96 qubits. As it is not trivial to simulate 96 qubits on an ordinary classical computer, it was far more convenient to compose the movements using quantum hardware.

1 Introduction

Stanislaw Ulam and John von Neumann conceived the notion of Cellular Automata (CA) in the 1960s [1]. A cellular automaton is a discrete computational model consisting of a grid of cells, each in one of a finite number of values, that evolve over time according to a set of rules based on the values of neighboring cells. The number of possible values for the cells might simply be the two numbers 1 and 0 (represented on a grid by the colours black and white, respectively), but it can be any amount. Depending on the application, the cells can represent formulas, algorithms, processors, systems, and music. CA are known to produce evolving patterns (Figure 1). Music is the art of organising sounds in space and time. Hence, I am interested in leveraging CA to compose music. These CA patterns remind me of musical forms, such as variations on a theme [2, 3, 4].

Figure 1: A pattern produced by nine cycles of a PQCA.

2 Quantum Cellular Automata

Quantum Cellular Automata (QCA) were introduced as an alternative paradigm for quantum computation and were shown to behave as a Turing machine [5]. In QCA, the cells are implemented with qubits. However, implementing a QCA with currently available quantum hardware is not trivial because of the so-called non-cloning theorem of quantum mechanics. The difficulty lies in updating all qubits in the same cycle. The general state of a CA at a certain time t is characterized by two properties: its current state and an update function that establishes the values of cells at time $t + 1$. Thus, we need to apply an update circuit to all qubits of the automaton simultaneously at each time step. Several approaches have been proposed to mitigate this difficulty [5]. One of them is referred to as Partitioned Quantum Cellular Automata (PQCA). For a rigorous theoretical discussion, please refer to [6, 7], in particular, to learn more about their non-classical behaviour.

In PQCA, we first define one or more *partition* schemes to divide an arrangement of cells into tessellating *supercells* [8]. Then, a *global update circuit* is built from *update frames*. These update frames are defined using the partitions and *local circuits*. To understand this, let us consider a 4×4 grid of cells, as shown on the left side of Figure 2.

Figure 2: A grid of 4×4 cells (on the left side) partitioned into horizontal pairs of cells (in the middle) and vertical strips of four cells each (on the right side.)

Figure 2 shows two examples of partitions: one is a partition of the grid into horizontal strips and the other into vertical strips, respectively. Effectively, the partition in the middle constitutes eight supercells, each of which is formed by two cells. The partition on the right side makes four supercells, each of which is formed by four cells.

Now, let us define a global update circuit. A global update circuit can and should include more than one update frame. For this example, let us define two local circuits, one for each of the partitions,

Figure 3: Local update circuits. Whereas the one on the left is made of two qubits for the horizontal partition, the one on the right is made of four qubits for the vertical partition.

as shown in Figure 3: one for the horizontal partitions and another for the vertical partitions. They yield two update frames. The tessellation of these frames results in a global update circuit with 16 qubits, one qubit per cell of the 4×4 grid, shown in Figure 4. An example of a pattern produced by nine iterations of this PQCA is shown in Figure 1.

To begin with, the qubits of the PQCA should normally start in the ground state $|0\rangle$. Then, for each subsequent cycle, the qubits are initialized with the respective measurements of the previous cycle. The **X** gate is used to flip the initial state of those qubits that need to be initialized as $|1\rangle$.

Figure 4: A global update circuit.

3 Music Mapping

The art of generating music with CA hinges on the methods to convert their outputs into music. Previous experiments with mapping designs for classical CA and PQCA can be found in [9, 8].

For *Qubism*, a PQCA grid was treated as a structural frame for a musical segment. As shown in the example below, this amounts to two measures of music. The values of the cells specify how the contents are arranged inside the structural frame, or measures. The vertical dimension of the grid defines the number of tracks (or instruments). The horizontal dimension defines the length of the segment and encodes a

transposition coefficient. Each column of the grid is associated to a beat in a $\frac{4}{4}$ measure. As an example, consider the 8×4 grid of cells depicted in Figure 5. Let us hypothesise this is the output from a PQCA cycle. This grid provides a frame for two $\frac{4}{4}$ measures: eight columns, four columns per measure. Thus, each cycle of the PQCA will generate two measures of music at a time. In this case, because the grid has four rows, the music will have four tracks. This particular example yields three notes because there are only three cells equal to 1 (i.e., coloured black). Two notes are played by the instrument allocated to track number three and one note by the instrument for track number two. How are the pitches, timing placements, and durations of the notes calculated?

Figure 5: A 8×4 grid of cells. Three cells are equal to 1.

3.1 Calculating the Pitch of a Cell

The pitches are picked from sets of *reference pitches*. The sets are labelled as 00, 01, 10 and 11, respectively. In the example in Figure 6, each set contains four reference pitches each.

Figure 6: Sources of reference pitches.

Given a cell that is equal to 1, the system builds a two-bit long code (xy) with the values of the top right (x) and bottom left (y) neighbours of the cell (Figure 7) to establish from which set to pick a reference pitch. For example, in Figure 5, the cell in coordinates (5,2) gives the code (10): $x = 1$ and $y = 0$. Thus, the system retrieves the first pitch, A3, from set 10. The system loops through a pitch set sequentially; the next time it needs to retrieve a reference pitch from this set, it will pick the second one, E4, and so on.

Those pitches in the sets are referred to as references because they are not necessarily the pitch that will be outputted. They may be transposed. The system has a list of transposition coefficients $\Delta = [\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_n]$. These coefficients correspond to semitones for transposing a given reference pitch. That is,

the system transposes the selected reference pitch by adding to (or subtracting from) a transposition coefficient δ .

Let us consider the following example: $\Delta = [7, -5, 0, 12, 4, 0, 5, -7]$. Δ must be of the same length as the horizontal dimension of the grid; in this case, equal to eight. This is because the x coordinate of the cell defines the index i of $\Delta[i]$ to retrieve the respective coefficient to transpose a pitch. Thus, for cell (5, 2) it will add four semitones ($\Delta[5] = 4$) to pitch $A3$, resulting in $C\sharp4$. Therefore, $C\sharp4$ is the pitch of the cell (5, 2).

Figure 7: Scheme for calculating musical codes.

3.2 Placing the Pitches in the Frame

There may be up to eight different options for note durations, each of which also has a binary code associated with it (Figure 8); these associations are arbitrary.

	= 111		= 011
	= 100		= 000
	= 101		= 001
	= 110		= 010

Figure 8: Binary codes for the waiting times and durations.

As mentioned above, the 8×4 grid in Figure 5 defines a frame for two $\frac{4}{4}$ measures of music. We already established that the cell (5, 2) yields the pitch $C\sharp4$, which is to be played by the second instrument (counting from the bottom to the top of the score) of an ensemble of four (Figure 9). To calculate the placement of this pitch on the frame, the system builds two codes based on the values of the respective neighbouring cells, as shown in Figure 7: (abc) for Wait and (mno) for Duration. Thus, $\text{Wait}_{(5,2)} = 000$ and $\text{Duration}_{(5,2)} = 000$. This code retrieves a half note. In this case, note $C\sharp4$ starts after two beats from the beginning and lasts for another two beats. The complete frame with all three notes is shown in Figure 9. The cells were processed from the bottom to the top and from the left to the right of the grid, in this order: (5, 2), (2, 3) and (6, 3). It turns out that all

the notes in this example start at the same time and have the same duration.

There are often cases where the resulting note for a cell is identical to one that exists already. In these cases, the duplicating note is discarded.

Figure 9: The musical rendering of the grid in Figure 5.

We are now in a position to examine how the system generated materials - or musical forms - for *Observe* and *Revisit*.

Figure 10: The global update circuit for *Observe* and *Revisit*.

4 Composing *Observe* and *Revisit*

First, I set the PQCA grid to 8×12 cells. Thus, each cycle produced two $\frac{4}{4}$ measures of music for twelve tracks. Then, I established two PQCA partition schemes, forming 48 supercells each. One scheme partitioned the grid into horizontal pairs of cells and

Figure 11: Another local update circuit made of two qubits.

the other into vertical pairs. Next, I defined two update frames, one for each partition.

The respective local update circuits require two qubits each. One of them is the 2-qubit circuit displayed on the left side of Figure 3. The other is shown in Figure 11. The resulting global update circuit is shown in Figure 10. As it used 96 qubits, only a partial view of the circuit is shown. Concerning the music elements, I created a set of four 12-tone series, as shown in Figure 12. I specified binary codes for the waiting times and durations differently from those shown in Figure 8, but still with 3 digits.

Figure 12: Sources of reference pitches.

Figure 13: Resulting musical form for twelve instruments.

While experimenting with various parameters, I felt the results were not conveying a sense of musical form to me. I improved this by setting the parameters with considerable redundancy to promote

more repetitions in the generated materials. With all qubits starting in the ground state $|0\rangle$, I ran the system for 50 cycles, 80,000 shots per cycle. Figure 14 depicts the cellular sequence resulting from the first four cycles of the PQCA. Figure 13 shows the respective resulting musical forms produced by the first two cycles; i.e., two measures per cycle.

Figure 14: Cellular sequence resulting from the first four cycles of the PQCA.

The output of the system was considered as raw materials with which I then composed the piece. Metaphorically, think of a sculptor designing a work of art by cutting and carving forms from a block of plaster or stone. The acts of composing for the acoustic strings and the electronic part took place in synchrony. With two screen monitors attached to my computer, I uploaded the output MIDI file to Sibelius¹ and Logic Pro² and displayed them on different screens.

To compose for the strings, I selected clusters from the generated score and crafted them into a new score. This process consisted of the unfolding of the clusters into sequences, instrumentation, and orchestration. I occasionally deleted notes from clusters, but have not added any notes to them. I used extended techniques significantly, in a quest to achieve unorthodox timbres, especially when combined with electroacoustic materials. Examples of this process can be seen in Figures 13 and 15. Highlighted with dashed lines in Figure 13 are materials crafted into the score in Figure 15. For instance, cluster number 1 became a sequence of three notes for the second violins, played pizzicato and very loudly.

In Logic Pro, the compositional process involved allocating synthesised electronic instruments and sampled sounds to the tracks and changing the volume here and there. The clusters that were picked for the strings were not removed from the tracks for

¹A score writer and editor application, developed by Sibelius Software, which is now part of Avid.

²A Digital Audio Workstation and MIDI sequencer application developed by Apple Inc.

the electronics. Furthermore, the clusters were not modified and their time positions remained intact. This ensured that the form of the music remained faithful to the structure generated by the PQCA. The only modification I made occasionally here was to shift materials from one track to another on a measure-by-measure basis. I did this mainly because the system generated 12 tracks, but I decided to compose for eight channels. Musically speaking, the electronics are intended to expand, or embellish, the timbres of the strings. Performance requires precise synchronisation between the ensemble and the electronics.

I set the system with 96 qubits because I wanted to use as many qubits as possible at the time, fitting the frame of two $\frac{4}{4}$ measures. The largest quantum computer I had access to when I started working on this piece sported 127 superconducting qubits, built by IBM Quantum. The system was implemented in Python and Qiskit³. The system generates music notation in MusicXML format using Music21⁴.

Figure 15: An excerpt from the composition.

5 Concluding Remarks

There have been a few preliminary signs of the advantages that quantum computers promise to bring over classical ones (e.g. [10, 11]). But I am not in a position here to advocate any quantum advantage for musical applications. Furthermore, my research does not seek for a quantum advantage. Rather, I am interested in “quantum difference”.

I would like to clarify that the method that I developed to render music from PQCA outputs is, of course, arbitrary. There are infinite ways to do this. Let me emphasise that, in my opinion, the design of such method is an integral part of a creative compositional process. The tools and materials on hand influence how one creates. The act of composing with pencil and paper on the piano is definitely different

³<https://www.ibm.com/quantum/qiskit>

⁴<https://www.music21.org>

from composing with generative software on a laptop, let alone quantum computing software. Be that as it may, I should mention that I was unable to run the circuit in Figure 10 with a quantum computer simulator on a top-of-the-range Apple Mac Studio. I would not argue that it would have been impossible to compose this piece without a quantum computer. However, if I were to program this PQCA with, say, 1,024 qubits (e.g., $16 \times \frac{4}{4}$ measures for 16 instruments), then the challenge might have been very different. I hope to be able to work with thousands of qubits to compose music using algorithms that can only run on quantum computers. Would this lead to a different kind of aesthetics? This is the million-dollar question.

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6 References

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